

THE IMPACT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ON A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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ABSTRACT

The article touches upon the issues of the importance of physical culture and sports for student youth. The influence of physical education and sports on health, on physical development, upbringing, a healthy lifestyle.

Currently, there are a lot of problems in life that affect all aspects of human life. The political, economic, social situation is changing, universal human values remain unchanged, the value of which defies criticism: one of these values is physical culture, sports.

Physical culture has a significant impact on the development of young people, being an integral part of the general culture. Its positive influence can be realized if it is based on the natural science basis of the theory of physical education, which is closely related to physiology, hygiene, anatomy and other sciences. In universities, physical culture is presented as the most important basic component of the formation of the general culture of students, a means of creating a harmoniously developed personality

This problem is especially relevant for students of colleges and institutes, since during the student years the foundations of a healthy lifestyle are formed and laid, and physical education is not always a priority. At the same time, the academic load on

students is enormous, which often harms their general physical and mental state, and this can especially negatively affect the process of personality formation, which coincides with the period of study in an educational institution. It is necessary to consider the concept of "physical culture" as a combination of a student's physical development, the state of his physical and mental health and "physical culture" itself as a component of the cultural development of a personality. In universities, physical culture is presented as the most important basic component of the formation of the general culture of students, a means of creating a harmoniously developed personality

The relevance of this formulation of the problem stems from the new course of social and, in particular, youth policy, where the main place is given to all areas of "healthier society." The modern situation is such that young people often do not have a real opportunity to raise the level of physical culture. There is a point of view, according to which, the lack of an adequate

level of development of sports and promotion of physical culture gives rise to an increasing spread of such “diseases of society” as nicotine addiction, alcoholism, including “beer alcoholism”, drug addiction, mainly among the youth. There is an opinion about the direct dependence of the demographic, and hence the economic situation in the country on the level of physical culture of the population.

To study the influence of physical culture on the process of personality formation and the choice of professional activity, it is necessary to take into account both permanent and temporary conditions that set the student the task of improving his physical condition and health. A positive effect from physical education will be achieved only when complex, long and intense physical exercises correspond to the individual capabilities of a person, the conditions of his life and work. But, an important role of physical culture throughout a person's life.

The importance of physical culture and sports for the health, development and general condition of young people can hardly be exaggerated. From an early age, parents, educators, the media - radio and television - instill in the child the unique benefits of physical activity and encourage children to actively participate in sports. At this age, sports activities are usually supervised by experienced coaches and specialists who monitor the correct and harmonious development of a growing body. At school age, this role is mainly performed by physical education teachers at school. By the age of 16, a person's self-awareness is sufficiently formed. From that moment on, sports activities turn into serious activities that bring joy. The positive aspect is that sport contributes to the

development of communication skills, relieves complexes and liberates; physical activity, active movement have a very beneficial effect on success in mental work, which is by no means superfluous for students. Along with this comes the need to independently assess their physical capabilities and, in accordance with this, to really calculate their strengths. Engaged in physical exercises, students learn the patterns of development of physical qualities, motor skills and abilities, acquire knowledge about the structure and functions of the body and its systems, which expands its educational level. Physical education is a very complex and multifunctional psychophysiological process, especially in conditions when people pay insufficient attention to physical culture

The subject of physical culture, which is taught in colleges, institutes, forms another layer in the general physical condition of a person, his health, physical fitness and physical perfection. Physical education is, first of all, the prevention of various diseases and, first of all, hypertension and coronary heart disease. These diseases are often observed by technical specialists and require long-term treatment. But it doesn't always lead to recovery. Their prevention has a significant effect. In the process of exercising, working capacity increases. This is evidenced by the increasing ability of a person to do a lot of work in a certain period of time. With an increase in working capacity in a state of muscular rest, the heart rate decreases, students begin to work harder, but at the same time less fatigue. Rest and, above all, sleep is fully utilized by the body. The professional activity of the students of the institute implies physical work, which

means that such a person must have good physical shape and excellent health. And all this can be achieved by regularly doing physical education and sports.

In recent years, the role of science in the creation of pedagogical technologies that are adequate to the level of public knowledge has been increasing. We tested the technologies of physical education that can improve traditional physical education, have a positive effect on health and harmony of physical development, as well as on the formation of motor abilities. Physical education teachers form an interest in physical exercises and the need for a healthy lifestyle, using non-standard forms of classes for their development, improvement and health promotion: dance, yoga, play, as well as active teaching methods and new health technologies: aerobics, step - aerobics, stretching aerobics, etc.

The importance of the physical fitness of student youth, due to the need for an effective workforce at this stage of the development of society, is becoming increasingly important. In addition, physical education and sports gives a person not only a sense of physical perfection, but also gives him strength and shapes his spirit. Raises the level of moral qualities, which is so necessary for today's society. Physical culture takes on colossal importance in the process of personality formation, when it affects him from different sides, forms moral qualities, spirit, and affects the physical condition, stimulating a new approach to life and work, new achievements.

In order to consciously come to the conclusion and the importance of physical culture and sports, students must understand its role in their lives. And it is

very good if they understand it not too late in order to start leading a healthy lifestyle. Physical education is a purposeful process of influencing a person for his physical improvement, development and education. Education is viewed as a body of knowledge acquired in a social way, it is a specific form of socialization. As noted by S.V. Shevchenko, E.S. Romanenko, L.A. Sitak is a culturally determined and culturally significant activity aimed at preserving and retransmitting the knowledge of a given society in order to preserve it by forming a certain type of society and a certain type of personality

Sport and physical culture is not only a healthy lifestyle - it is generally a normal and healthy life, which opens up more and more opportunities for the realization of strengths and talents. This is the path on which a sane person enters, so that the life he has lived would be fruitful, bring joy to himself and those around him. The progressive rhythm of life requires more and more physical activity and preparedness of young people. All the increasing loads that fall on the shoulders of the younger generation throughout their lives require a higher physical perfection, which must be achieved through physical education.

Any person, regardless of age, wants to be happy and most importantly healthy, and physical education can help him with this. But health cannot be bought or received as a gift. Therefore, you need to do everything to preserve it. Usually, due to an improper lifestyle, a person develops nervous disorders, various diseases, problems at work and at home. But you just need to think: are we doing everything possible to preserve our health? After all, often visits to the doctor can be avoided if

you build your lifestyle correctly. Physical culture implements its educational and developmental functions most fully in the purposeful pedagogical process of physical education, which contributes to the

formation of moral and volitional qualities, improves social adaptation, effectively resists the negative consequences of nervous tension and stress.

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